

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B191
Date: 25 Apr 2006
Take Off 09:59:25
Landing: 14:29:22
Flight Time 4h29m57

Campaign: ICEPIC (cancelled following fault, became BBR characterisation flight)
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Mull

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Hayward	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Wet Neph	Simon Osborne	Met Office
8	Core Chem / CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
9	Core Chem Training	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
10	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
11	CPI Training	Karl Beswick	Manchester University
12	Wet Neph	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Miss Sci 2 / Wet Neph train	Ben Johnson	Met Office
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B191 Track 25-APR-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b191
 Date: 25 April 2006
 Project: BBR Cals
 Location: North Scotland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094155		inu to nav	0.29 kft	137	
094215		engine start	0.29 kft	137	
094504		power change	0.29 kft	137	
094701		taxy	0.29 kft	136	start
095233		QNH	0.30 kft	174	1015mb Cranfield
095925		T/O	0.28 kft	212	from Cranfield
100328		jw/nevz zero	4.5 kft	359	
100451		asp open	6.4 kft	357	
111009	112148	Profile 1	20.0 - 30.0 kft	022	
112555	113111	Run 1.1	30.0 kft	341	
112747		contrails	30.0 kft	344	intermittent
113239	113739	Run 1.2	30.1 - 30.0 kft	254	
113947	114447	Run 1.3	30.0 kft	167	
114618		contrails	30.1 kft	082	
114637	115140	Run 1.4	30.0 kft	080	
115342	115927	Profile 2	30.1 - 32.0 kft	313	
115656		contrails	31.3 kft	310	stopped
115927	120444	Run 2.1	32.0 kft	309	
120628	121132	Run 2.2	32.1 - 32.0 kft	223	
121306	121809	Run 2.3	32.1 - 32.0 kft	139	
122010	122518	Run 2.4	32.0 kft	048	
122906	124104	Run 3.1	32.0 - 32.1 kft	188	pitch oscs at start
122958		contrails	32.0 kft	188	intermittent
124115	124710	Profile 3	32.1 - 34.0 kft	190	
124711	125401	Run 4.1	34.0 - 33.9 kft	194	pitch oscs at start
130415		contrails	28.9 kft	233	stop
140009		asp closed	13.6 kft	137	
142922		Land	0.27 kft	212	at Cranfield
143608		standstill	0.28 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B191 Track 25-APR-06

FAAM Sortie Brief*ICEPIC: Study of the development of cumulus clouds*Flight No: B191Date: 25th April 2006Trial objectives:

To investigate the development of cumulus clouds over the UK.

Location:

In developing Cu clouds over NW Scotland (suggest East of 6°W, and south of 57.5°N).

Weather:

Either individual, or groups of Cu cloud.

Special requirements:

None

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 11:00L.
2. Transit to the operating region at FL200 and identify suitable area for operations (80mins).
3. Perform stepped profile descent from FL200 to 500ft ASL (below cloud base) at 1000ft/minute (100mins).
4. Perform a SLR below cloud for 10minutes in a direction determined by the mission scientist (110mins).
5. Turn onto reciprocal heading and perform a SLR at 500ft below cloud for ten minutes (125mins).
6. Ascend to around the 0C or 500ft below the cloud top (130mins).
7. Perform a penetration with wings level through the cloud (140mins).
8. If a single cloud is large and clearly identifiable and the cloud is continuing to develop, make a reciprocal turn while ascending by ~1000ft and repeat the cloud penetration several times (180mins).
9. If the cloud is not large or discrete, then proceed to the next cumulus cell, and repeat the penetrations at approximately 0C for a 10minute interval. Perform reciprocal turn while climbing by intervals of 3C and repeat 10minute runs (180mins).
10. Continue 8 and 9 as time permits (270mins).
11. Recover and land at Prestwick (300mins).
12. Refuel at Prestwick (390mins).
13. Take of from Prestwick (17:30L).
14. Transit to Cranfield and land (18:30L).

Note) – clouds should be continuing to develop – if red echos on the aircraft radar, or decrease in cloud top, or heavily glaciated then move on to next cloud.

Debrief for Flight B191 on 25th April 2006

Sortie Objectives: Originally B191 was planned to be an ICEPIC flight aiming to make penetrations of developing cumulus shower clouds at temperatures from 0 to -15C. However, due to the failure of a de-icing heater (right pitot) the original sortie had to be abandoned 30 minutes after take off. An alternative sortie was carried out flying box patterns at high altitude to test the vertically pointing broadband radiometers (BBRs).

Weather: Extensive low and high cloud across much of the UK ahead of a cold front that oriented southwest-northeast through Scotland.

Operating area: Over northwest Scotland and the ocean beyond the northern coast.

Flight Patterns: Subsequent to take-off, a transit was made heading northwest at FL200 towards Glasgow. The right pitot heater failed shortly after take off making the aircraft vulnerable to icing. Consequently a decision was made to continue to the operating region of Northwest Scotland and carry out two box patterns for the purpose of examining the response of the vertically pointing BBRs to the heading of the aircraft with respect to the solar azimuth angle. The first box was to be with legs taking headings of 0, 90, 180 and 270 from the azimuth. The second box was to have legs with headings 45, 135, 225, and 315 from azimuth. For modelling of the BBR fluxes it was essentially to have cloud free sky above the aircraft. Thick, extensive cirrus sheets were observed above during the transit to the operating area. Satellite telephone communications with staff at HQ in Exeter informed us that cirrus cloud was present over most of Scotland but that there were cirrus free areas in the far north of Scotland and beyond. On arriving in the operating area a climb was made to FL300 aiming to ascend above the cirrus. Eventually a sufficiently large cirrus free region was found over north Scotland and the two box patterns were carried out. The first box pattern was at FL300 with the first leg down sun (180 degrees from Azimuth) on a heading of 340 degrees and subsequent legs following in an anticlockwise direction. Azimuth was 160-165 degrees and zenith angle was approximately 45 degrees during the first box pattern.

Significant contrailing occurred during the later two legs of the box pattern and a small amount of ice was registered by the 2D cloud physics probes during the final leg of the box (across sun at 75 degrees). At the end of the box pattern a profile was made up to FL320 to rise into drier air above for the second box pattern. Contrailing ceased during the ascent and did not occur for the second box pattern. There were no incidences of ice crystals register by cloud physics for the second box pattern.

Very high levels of ozone were recorded during both box patterns suggesting an intrusion of stratospheric air from a tropopause fold over that region.

On completion of the box patterns a run was made travelling south into the sun (at the azimuth angle, which was 190 degrees at that time). A series of pitch oscillations were made the aircraft for a period of approximately five minutes to vary the angle of the BBRs with respect to the zenith. The pitch oscillated from 3 to 7 degrees at a frequency of about 4 per minute. The altitude did not vary by more than 100ft during the oscillations (FL320 +/- 50ft). This led to variations of +/- 30 Wm⁻² in the upward facing BBR measuring total solar irradiance. Significant contrailing occurred during this run. The aircraft begun to enter the top of cirrus shortly after the oscillations were complete. A profile was made to FL340 to ascend above the cirrus, and another 5

minute series of oscillations was carried out. Ozone levels had decreased as the aircraft travelled south.

A transit was made back to Cranfield at FL340.

Summary: A successful flight for BBR testing.

Problems: Cloud particle imager (CPI) failed early in the flight. Whilst at high altitude it was noted that FWVS was reporting unphysically high values. SID2 U/S, SID1 data lost. PCASP poor at high altitude especially with channel 1 noise.

Ben Johnson

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.191** Date **25/4/06** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:00	—	0	—	Ganfield	Overcast, light occasional drizzle, poor visibility
11:00	—	0	215		T/O
10:02:00		FL200			Cloud base ~1500ft (lower layer) cloud top ~2000ft (of SC layers of cloud cloud above. 8/8)
10:07	—	8.5kft	0		freezing level at 8,500 ft
10:14:00		17kft	320		CPI having problems
10:16:00		FL200	320		Climbed to FL200 FL200
10:16:00					Wind 15-20 ms ⁻¹ 270°
					Cirrus above but clearing 50-100 miles ahead
10:20:00			330		Right Pitot heater failed. Deicing heating won't function therefore cloud penetrations are not safe and sortie plans must change. Box patterns at high altitude are now the only thing worth doing.
10:25:00		FL200	330		Aiming to do box pattern just off coast from Glasgow North of Glasgow.
10:45:00		FL200	310		Turned onto heading towards Glasgow
					cirrus sheets ahead but patchy.
					30 mins to operating area.
10:50		FL200	315		AZIMUTH = 150, ZENITH = 45
11:00		FL200	320	Glasgow	Continuing north to operating area, however thick cirrus now above.
11:09	P1	FL200	20		Start profile to FL300 aiming to climb above the cirrus
11:21:48	End P1	FL300	20		Turning onto heading 346° for down run SLR
11:25:53	R1.1	FL300	346		End AZIMUTH = 160°
11:30:11	End R1.1	FL300	345		contrailing, but now stopped by during run end of run.
11:32:30	Start R1.2	FL300	255		

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B191** Date **25/04/06** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:33:00	R1.2	FL300	255		Ozone levels extremely high
	"	"	"		Either stratospheric air or instrument problems.
11:38	End R1.2	"	255		Probably a tropopause fold.
11:40	Start R1.3	"	165		BBRs looking good.
11:44:30		"	165		Contrailing significantly during R1.3. ozone still high.
11:44:42	End R1.3	"	165		
11:46:37	Start R1.4	"	75		FWVS is faulty, showing v. high values.
11:53	End R1.4	"	75		Saw some cirrus particle so decided to climb to FL320 for next box pattern.
		"	75		
11:55:42	P2	FL310	316		contrails peter out at FL310
11:57:22	Start 2.1	"	316		
11:59:27	End P2	"	315		No cirrus encountered
	Start				High O ₃ values again
12:04:44	End 2.1	"	315		suspect we are in stratospheric air
12:06:28	Start 2.2	"	225		
12:11:32	End 2.2	"	225		
12:13:06	Start 2.3	"	140		Following box pattern a
12:18:09	End 2.3	"	140		run will commence with oscillations of pitch angle.
12:20:10	Start 2.4	"	50		
12:25:18	End 2.4	"	50		
12:29:06	Start R3	185	190		Angle oscillations up & dn.
12:30:00		"	190		Intermittently contrailing
12:35:00	End R3	"	190		End of oscillations
					Fluctuations of O ₃ & contrailing
					Contrails getting stronger to south getting more humid

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 191

Date: 25/4/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +1	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:10:08	Noise		50	10	Noise											Start Profile 1 from FL200	
11:11:17	Noise			10	Noise	12	200	200	200						10	FL210	
11:12:16	Noise			2	Noise			180								FL220	
11:13:18	Noise			5	Noise	11	200	230	200						10	FL230	
11:14:20	Noise			10	Noise	2	150	450	200						10	FL240	
11:15:20	Noise			5	Noise	1		Noise								FL250	
11:16:22	Noise			5	Noise	1		Noise								FL260 Rearm 2 1	
11:17:32	Noise			5	Noise			Noise								FL270	
11:18:45	Noise			5	Noise			Noise								FL280	
11:20:09	Noise			2	Noise			Noise								FL290	
11:21:45	Noise			2	Noise			Noise								End of Profile @ FL300	
11:25:54																Start Run 1.1 @ FL300	
11:26:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:28:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:30:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:31:14																End of Run 1.1	
11:32:38																Start Run 1.2 @ FL300	
11:33:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:35:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:37:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:37:40																End of Run 1.2	
11:39:37																Start Run 1.3 @ FL300	
11:40:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:42:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:44:00	Noise			15	Noise			Noise									
11:44:42																End of Run 1.3	
11:46:37																Start Run 1.4 @ FL300	
11:47:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:49:00	Noise			10	Noise			Noise									
11:51:00	Noise			20	Off			Noise								SID2 detector voltage 2KV – maybe shorting	
11:51:40																End of Run 1.4	
11:53:42	Noise			20				Noise								Start Profile 2 from FL300	
11:56:30	Noise			10				Noise								FL310	
11:59:27																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL320	
12:00:00	Noise			5				Noise									
12:02:00	Noise			5				Noise									
12:04:00	Noise			5				Noise									
12:04:42																End of Run 2.1	
12:06:31																Start Run 2.2 @ FL320	
12:07:00	Noise			5				Noise									
12:09:00	Noise			5				Noise									
12:11:00	Noise			5				Noise									
12:11:30																End of Run 2.2	
12:13:04																Start Run 2.3 @ FL320	
12:14:00	Noise			10				Noise									
12:16:00	Noise			5				Noise									

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.191**.....

 Date **25/04/06**

 Operator's name: **OSBORNE/WILSON**

 Page **1** of **1**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow (lpm)	Dry neph RH (%)	Wet neph RH (%)	Temp ramp	T _{water} (°C)	Remarks
0730	PRE-FLIGHT		CHECKS					Time synch. with HORACE
			DRY Neph			zero		etc. 30 sec av. / 300 min BLANK
			WET Neph			zero		etc. " "
0830	GRAND		120	65.0	49.0	—	—	RH1 = 49.2% RH3 = 44.5%, RH5 = 53.0%
								⇒ Dry wet sensor looks suspect.
				ratio	for smaller wet			= 0.95.
								≅ 1.00 later after ~ 1 hour. running
								GOOD!!
1020				0%	19%	↗	10°C	set
102540	TRANSIT	R2200	12.4	0%	23.8%	↗	15°C	set
102940	"	R2200	12.5	0%	28.3%	↗	20°C	set now. 43.0%
103249	"	R2200	12.5	0%	35.7%	↗	25°C	set now. RH1 = 7.0% / RH3 = 3.6% / RH5 = 34.0%
103515	"	R2200	12.5	0%	46.3%	↗	30°C	set now. RH5 = 60.0%
103820	"	"	12.3	0%	58.7%	↗	35°C	set now. RH5 = 80.6%. large difference between RH5 + RH6 (wet neph)
104559	"	"	12.5	0%	66.6%	↗	38°C	set now (38°C). RH5 = 84.5%
104716	"	"	12.5	0%	72.0%	↗	40°C	set now increase by 2°C
10505	"	"	12.5	0%	80.2%	↗	42°C	set now. RH5 = 95.0%. T _{in} = 21.9°C
105541	"	"	12.4	0%	84.5%	↗	43°C	set now. RH5 = 97.3%
110120	"	"	12.4	0%		↓	5°C	set to 5°C → min. temp

114700 STOP RECORDING TO LABVIEW (keep ~~with~~ DRY Neph into HORACE, manually)

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 191** Date: 25th April 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	Y
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	N	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B191

Date: 25 April 2006

Instruments

1. Core Chem CO gases and lamp not turned on pre-flight (possible warm-up time issue on CO data at start of flight).
2. Can't do y-x plots on horace data display
3. FWVS data not valid – U/S
4. Total Water status light on for majority of the high part of the flight – went back off at FL210/-30C on descent.

Aircraft

Right Pitot Heater Failure – sortie could not be completed as planned (could not fly in icing conditions)

Satcom Calls

1 – Jim Hayward

New plot, same times

Pitch $7^{\circ} \rightarrow 3^{\circ}$

⊙ All
○
○

New plot, same times

⊙ All
C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B191:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x Upward Facing Cameras
2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

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